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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

OQOVA SUVLARNI TOZALASH TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ekologik, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy barqarorlikni o'z ichiga olgan ko'rsatkichlar to'plami ishlab chiqilgan va turli xil chiqindi suvlarni tozalash texnologiyalarining barqarorligini o'rgangan olimlar ishlari o'rganilgan. Tanlangan iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar kapital, ekspluatatsiya va boshqaruv va foydalanuvchi xarajatlari edi, chunki ular ma'lum bir texnologiyaning jamiyat uchun iqtisodiy qulayligini belgilaydi. Atrof-muhit ko'rsatkichlari energiyadan foydalanishni o'z ichiga oladi, chunki u bilvosita resurslardan foydalanishni va biokimyoviy kislorodga bo'lgan talab, ammiak azoti, fosfor va patogenlar kabi an'anaviy chiqindi suv tarkibiy qismlarini olib tashlashda texnologiyaning ishlashini o'Ichaydi. Ushbu ko'rsatkichlar reusni ham aniqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: oqova, texnologiya, chiqindi, kislorod, gigiyena, sanitariya.

Global sog'liqni saqlash va sanitariya holatini yaxshilash va natijada kasallik tarqalishining kamayishi asosan gigiyena qoidalariga, sog'liqni saqlash muassasalarining mavjudligiga va oqava suvlarni ishonchli yig'ish va tozalashga bog'liq. Jahon Sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) 2.4 milliard odam har qanday sanitariya-texnik vositalardan (JSST va BMT bolalar jamg'armasi, 2000) foydalanish imkoniyatiga ega emasligini taxmin qilmoqda. Oqava suvlarni yig'ish tizimlari (ya'ni kanalizatsiya tarmoqlari) va markazlashtirilgan va markazlashtirilmagan tozalash tizimlari asosan inson va atrof-muhit salomatligini himoya qilish uchun ishlab chiqilgan va boshqariladi [1]. Ularning afzalliklari keng tan olingan bo'lsa-da, ushbu infratuzilma va unga bog'liq texnologiyalarning boshqa jihatlari ham bor, ular unchalik aniq emas va shuning uchun kamroq tan olinadi, ammo ular jamoalarga va atrofdagi muhitga ta'sir qiladi. Masalan, kanalizatsiya tarmog'ining ijobiy tomoni chiqindi suvlarni tegishli tozalash inshootlariga yig'ish va tashishdir patogenlar va kimyoviy tarkibiy qismlar kabi kislorodni yo'q qilish o'rganiladi. Oqova suvlarni tozalash texnologiyasi turli ifloslantiruvchi moddalardan suvni tozalash va uni qayta ishlatishga yoki xavfsiz tarzda tabiatga qaytarishga yo'naltirilgan jarayonlar majmuasidir. Bu texnologiyalar sanoat, kommunal va qishloq xo'jalik oqova suvlari uchun qo'llaniladi.

Oqova suvlarni tozalash asosan uch bosqichda amalga oshiriladi: **Mexanik tozalash, biologik tozalash, kimyoviy tozalash bo'lib bu bosqichda suv tarkibidagi yirik zarrachalar va qattiq moddalar ajratiladi. Quyidagi usullar qo'llaniladi: Panjara va to'rlar** – yirik chiqindilar (yaproqlar, plastmassa, qog'oz va boshqalar) ushlab qolinadi. **Cho'ktirish havzalari (settling tanks)** – qum,

shag'al va boshqa og'ir zarrachalar cho'ktirib olinadi. **Suv sirtidan yog' va moylarni ajratish** – maxsus separatorlar orqali yog'lar yig'iladi.

Biologik tozalash bu usul mikroorganizmlar yordamida organik moddalarni parchalanishiga asoslangan. **Aerob usul** – bakteriyalar kislorod ishtirokida organik moddalarning parchalanishiga yordam beradi. **Anaerob usul** – kislorodsiz muhitda organik moddalar parchalanadi va natijada biogaz (metan) hosil bo'ladi. **Biofiltrlar** – suv filtrlar orqali bakteriyalar bilan tozalash jarayonidan o'tadi [2].

Kimyoviy reagentlar yordamida suvdagi zararli moddalar neytrallanadi yoki cho'ktiriladi. **Koagulyatsiya va flokulyatsiya** – maxsus kimyoviy moddalar (alyuminiy sulfat, temir xlorid) suvda erigan mayda zarrachalarni yirik zarrachalarga birlashtiradi va cho'ktirishga yordam beradi. **Dezinfeksiya** – bakteriyalar va viruslarni yo'qotish uchun ishlatiladi. Buning uchun quyidagi usullar qo'llaniladi: **Xlorlash** – suvga xlor yoki uning birikmalari qo'shiladi. **Ozonlash** – suvga ozon berish orqali mikroorganizmlar yo'q qilinadi. **Ultrabinafsha (UV) nurlanish** – mikroorganizmlarni yo'qotishda ishlatiladi. Ba'zi hollarda qo'shimcha yoki maxsus tozalash texnologiyalari ham qo'llaniladi: **Membranali filtratsiya (reverse osmosis, ultrafiltratsiya)** – suvni chuqur tozalash va ichimlik suvi sifatiga yetkazish. **Adsorbsiya** – ko'mir yoki zeolit kabi moddalar yordamida suv tarkibidagi zararli gazlar yoki kimyoviy moddalar ajratiladi [3].

Xulosa: Oqova suvlarni tozalash texnologiyalari global sog'liqni saqlash va sanitariya sharoitlarini yaxshilashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Jahon Sog'liqni saqlash tashkiloti (JSST) ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, dunyoda 2.4 milliarddan ortiq odam sanitariya-texnik vositalardan foydalanish imkoniyatiga ega emas, bu esa kasalliklarning keng tarqalishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Oqova suvlarni tozalash tizimlari inson salomatligi va atrof-muhitni himoya qilish uchun ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, ular mexanik, biologik va kimyoviy tozalash bosqichlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu bosqichlar orqali yirik chiqindilar, organik va kimyoviy ifloslantiruvchi moddalar samarali ravishda ajratib olinadi. Shuningdek, qo'shimcha texnologiyalar (membranali filtratsiya, adsorbsiya va boshqalar) yordamida suv chuqur tozalanib, ichimlik suvi sifatiga yetkazilishi yoki xavfsiz ravishda tabiatga qaytarilishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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